

Supplementary Appendix – Evaluation Structure, Performance Index Logic, and Applied Example of the BPESystem

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BPESystem is an integrated building performance evaluation framework, developed based on the Design Science Research (DSR) approach. The method is structured around a hierarchical system of criteria and sub-criteria, designed to capture different dimensions of building performance during the use phase. Each sub-criterion is evaluated through an operational question, which guides the evaluator's qualitative judgment and is subsequently converted into an ordinal performance value.

This approach allows its application by both technical specialists and institutional users, enabling the integration between regulatory compliance assessment and the perception of performance in use. To ensure consistency and comparability of results, the method adopts a standardized aggregation procedure, which considers only the sub-criteria actually evaluated, excluding inapplicable items from the calculation.

This appendix presents, in an integrated manner, (i) the nature of the ordinal rating scale, (ii) the process of aggregating the results, and (iii) a practical example of applying the method.

NATURE OF THE ORDINAL RATING SCALE :

The BPESystem uses a standardized ordinal scale composed of five levels (0, 25, 50, 75, and 100), assigned to subcriteria based on the observed level of service.

This scale is ordinal in nature, where numerical values function as performance classification codes, not necessarily representing equivalent quantitative intervals. Thus, the assigned values should be interpreted as relative positions within a performance hierarchy.

The use of numerical values is operational in nature, allowing for the systematization of evaluations and the consolidation of results throughout the method's structure.

The resulting performance index should be understood as a composite ordinal index, in which the numerical values represent ordered levels of performance. Therefore, the values expressed as percentages constitute a scaling convention to facilitate interpretation and relative comparison between criteria and units, and do not imply metric equivalence between intervals.

PROCESS OF AGGREGATING THE RESULTS:

The consolidation of results occurs hierarchically, according to the following steps:

(i) Evaluation of subcriteria

Each subcriterion is evaluated individually, based on a structured question, receiving an ordinal performance value.

(ii) Exclusion of inapplicable items

Subcriteria considered inapplicable are excluded from the calculation, ensuring that only valid items comprise the result.

(iii) Performance calculation by criterion

The criterion value is obtained through normalized aggregation of the ordinal values assigned to the valid subcriteria , resulting in a composite performance index.

(iv) Classification by performance ranges

The results are subsequently interpreted into categories (e.g., Non-compliant, Certified), reinforcing the qualitative nature of the analysis.

This process allows for relative comparisons between units and between different evaluation perspectives, while maintaining internal consistency and traceability.

It is recognized that the use of an ordinal scale associated with numerical aggregation presents limitations from the perspective of measurement theory, especially regarding the assumption of equivalent intervals between categories. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as relative performance indicators, suitable for comparative analysis and pattern identification, and not as absolute quantitative measures. Comparisons should be understood in terms of trend and pattern, not metric precision. The analyses are exploratory in nature, consistent with the stage of development of the method.

APPLIED EXAMPLE – CRITERION IV: PHYSICAL ASPECTS OF THE BUILDING:

Criterion IV – Physical Aspects of the Building , in Basic Health Unit IV (UBS IV), is presented , considering the two perspectives: technical evaluation and institutional user evaluation.

Criterion IV is composed of the following sub-criteria:

1. Maintenance
2. Visual communication
3. Architectural composition
4. Efficient use of space
5. Furniture and ergonomics
6. Ceiling height
7. Level of cleanliness of the environments

Each subcriterion is evaluated through a specific question, as shown in Table 1.

The ordinal values assigned to the subcriteria can be defined by the evaluator based on multiple sources of information, depending on the nature of the evaluation and the availability of data. These sources may include:

- On-site observation, allowing for direct assessment of the physical conditions of the building and its spaces;
- Document analysis, including user manuals, architectural and engineering designs, regulatory standards, operating licenses, and other technical records — particularly in the case of technical assessments;
- Interviews with professionals responsible for the operation or management of the facility;
- Technical instruments or measuring devices, when objective measurements are required for specific criteria;
- User perception, particularly in evaluations conducted by unit coordinators, reflecting the operational experience of individuals who interact with the building daily.

The combination of these information sources allows the evaluator to assign ordinal performance values to the sub-criteria, reflecting both technical conditions and operational experience , depending on the perspective adopted in the evaluation.

In certain cases, some sub-criteria may not be applicable to the context of the building being evaluated, either because the corresponding environment does not exist in the project, or because it is irrelevant to the functional context of the unit. In these situations, the evaluator does not assign a value to the sub-criterion, leaving all options on the ordinal scale (0–25–50–75–100) blank in the evaluation instrument. The system automatically interprets these blank responses as "not applicable".

For calculation purposes, only sub-criteria with an applicability indicator equal to 1 are considered in the composition of the criterion index. Ordinal values equal to zero are retained in the calculation, since they represent valid evaluations associated with unsatisfactory performance. On the other hand, sub-criteria

without an assigned ordinal value are excluded, as they correspond to items not applicable to the analyzed context.

This standardization procedure aims to ensure that the added value of the criterion is determined exclusively based on the sub-criteria actually evaluated, preserving the internal consistency of the method and avoiding distortions resulting from the inclusion of irrelevant items.

By way of example, Tables 2 and 3 present the responses that were given to UBS PIV by the technical and coordinating users, respectively.

The technical assessment, based on specialized inspection, indicated a high level of compliance for the building, with a predominance of high ordinal values among the sub-criteria.

The assessment carried out by the unit coordinator reflected the daily experience of using the building, incorporating functional and operational aspects.

For calculation purposes, the following definition of applicability of the sub-criteria was adopted:

- Sub-criterion evaluated: $A_i = 1$
- Sub-criterion not applicable: $A_i = 0$

The performance index for a given criterion C is obtained through the normalized aggregation of the ordinal values assigned to the applicable sub-criteria. The number of valid sub-criteria is given by:

$$N_{valid} = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i$$

The normalized weight of each applicable sub-criterion is defined by:

$$w_i = \frac{1}{N_{valid}}$$

Given S_i the ordinal value assigned to the subcriterion i , its contribution to the criterion index is

expressed by:

$$C_i = S_i \times w_i$$

The aggregate value of the criterion is obtained by summing the individual contributions:

$$C = \sum C_i$$

In the examples in Tables 2 and 3, it was found that all seven subcriteria were effectively evaluated. Thus, the number of valid subcriteria corresponds to:

$$N_{valid} = \sum_{i=1}^7 1 = 7$$

Consequently, the normalized weight assigned to each subcriterion was uniform:

$$w_i = \frac{1}{7} 0,142857$$

If any sub-criterion is not evaluated—due to its inapplicability—the weight calculation will consider only the set of valid sub-criteria. In this case, the weights are redistributed proportionally among the sub-criteria that were actually evaluated, in order to ensure the consistency of the aggregation process and avoid distortions in the added value.

In summary, the BPESystem calculation procedure follows these steps:

- Identification of the sub-criteria associated with the criterion;
- Individual assessment of subcriteria using the ordinal scale (0–25–50–75–100);
- Verification of the applicability of each sub-criterion;

- Assignment of the applicability indicator;
- Determining the number of valid subcriteria;
- Calculation of normalized weights;
- Determining individual contributions;
- Aggregation of contributions to obtain the criterion value.

In the example analyzed, the technical evaluation indicated satisfactory overall performance, with high scores in aspects such as conservation, spatial organization, and construction conditions, resulting in an aggregate value of 89%. In turn, the institutional user evaluation showed greater variability in ordinal values, with a predominance of intermediate levels, resulting in an aggregate value of 61%.

The BPESystem classifies the aggregated values of the criteria into five performance levels (Table 4), allowing for standardized interpretation of the results. Thus, for Criterion IV – Physical Aspect of the Building, the following results were obtained:

- Technical evaluation: 89% — “Gold” rating;
- Coordinator's evaluation: 61% — "Bronze" rating.

The difference between the results highlights a significant discrepancy between technical compliance and user experience. While the technical evaluation reflects adherence to normative and constructive parameters, the user's perspective reveals functional and operational limitations not fully captured by specialized inspections. The procedure described in this appendix is systematically applied to all BPESystem criteria. The evaluation structure, based on the standardized aggregation of valid sub-criteria, seeks to ensure internal consistency, traceability of results, and methodological transparency in the construction of the ordinal performance index .

It should be noted that the performance index presented in this study should not be interpreted as a quantitative measure of an interval or ratio nature, but rather as a composite ordinal index, used for relative comparison, pattern identification, and to support the interpretation of building performance.

Table 1. Example of the evaluation protocol applied for Criterion IV - Physical Aspect of the Building.

Criterion	Subcriterion	Objective	Operational Issue
IV - Physical Aspect of The Buildi ng	Maintenance	Check the state of conservation of the property.	What is the state of conservation of the building?
	Visual Communication	Analyze whether the building has a visual identity appropriate to its use.	Does the building have a visual identity that gives the property individuality?
	Architectural Composition	Check if the architectural design is suitable for its intended use and surroundings.	How would you rate the architectural integration of the building with its surroundings?
	Effective Use of Space	Assess whether the layout allows for the proper use and circulation of people.	Did the layout allow for good division, organization, and use of the building?
	Furniture and Ergonomics	The furniture should be ergonomic, durable, comfortable, and aesthetically pleasing for its intended use, as well as easy to clean.	Is the furniture suitable for its intended use?
	Ceiling Height	Municipal building codes establish the height of rooms based on the building's use.	Are the ceiling heights in the rooms adequate?
	Level Of Environmental Cleaning	Assess the hygiene and disinfection of environments and equipment.	How would you rate the cleanliness level of the environments and equipment?

Table 2. Responses assigned to UBS PIV - Technical User

PROTOCOL				UBS PORTE IV – technical user						
Criterion	Subcriterion	0/1	Value	0	25	50	75	100	Assigned Value	Observation
IV - Physical Aspect of The Building	Maintenance	1.00	0.142857					100	14.2857	No cracks in the structure and in good condition for a new building.
	Visual Communication	1.00	0.142857					100	14.2857	The visual communication follows the municipality's identity, both externally and internally, in addition to displaying informational materials about the health department's programs on the walls and at the unit's entrance.
	Architectural Composition	1.00	0.142857					100	14.2857	
	Effective Use of Space	1.00	0.142857					100	14.2857	A diagram showing the flowchart for employees, patients, as well as recyclable and common solid waste, and hospital waste was approved.
	Furniture and Ergonomics	1.00	0.142857				75		10.7143	The furniture partially meets the standard design requirements.
	Ceiling Height	1.00	0.142857					100	14.2857	No complaints about the item.
	Level Of Environmental Cleaning	1.00	0.142857			50			7.1428	Due to a lack of staff assigned to cleaning duties, there is a reported deficit in the cleanliness conditions at the UBS (Basic Health Unit).
Total		7	1						89	

Table 3. Responses assigned to UBS PIV - Coordinating User

PROTOCOL				Primary Health Care Unit (UBS) - Coordinating User						
Criterion	Subcriterion	0/1	Value	0	25	50	75	100	Assigned Value	Observation
IV - Physical Aspect of The Building	Maintenance	1.00	0.142857			50			7.1428	
	Visual Communication	1.00	0.142857				75		10.7143	
	Architectural Composition	1.00	0.142857				75		10.7143	
	Effective Use of Space	1.00	0.142857			50			7.1428	
	Furniture and Ergonomics	1.00	0.142857			50			7.1428	
	Ceiling Height	1.00	0.142857			50			7.1428	
	Level Of Environmental Cleaning	1.00	0.142857				75		10.7143	
Total		7	1						61	

Table 4. Performance level classification

Ordinal value range	Performance Level
≤ 50	Non-compliant
51 – 70	Bronze
71 – 80	Silver
81 – 90	Gold
91 – 100	Platinum